

AUTO-CONTINUOUS POSITIVE AIRWAY PRESSURE COMPLIANCE IN OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNEA PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT Background: The most effective treatment method of OSAS is CPAP therapy. In this study, we aimed to determine the factors affecting the device compatibility in patients with OSAS who underwent auto-CPAP therapy. **Material and methods:** Patients with OSAS who underwent auto-CPAP therapy between July 2014 and May 2017 were included in our study. According to the CPAP compliance, patients were divided into two groups as group 1 with sufficient compliance and group 2 with insufficient compliance. The mean AHI values, average and minimum-maximum CPAP use periods, side effects related to device use, and follow-up ESS results were compared among the groups after 4 weeks of CPAP therapy. **Results:** A total of 240 patients with OSAS who underwent auto-CPAP therapy were included to our study. Mean duration of CPAP use was 26.15 ± 4.89 days, mean duration of device use for per night was 5.31 ± 1.32 hours and average compliance rate was 60.8% within 4 weeks for the whole study population. Significant differences were found between two groups regarding the side effects such as the skin irritation, device noises, and morning headache. Furthermore, device satisfaction, mean-AHI values and ESS scores were significantly different between the two groups. **Conclusion:** Side effects related to the CPAP mask determine the CPAP compliance rates among OSAS patients. We believe that detailed information about the difficulties that patients may encounter should be given to the patients before the onset of the therapy and eventually patients should be encouraged to use the device.

KEYWORDS Sleep apnea, compliance, CPAP, obstructive sleep apnea syndrome

Introduction

Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS) affects approximately 2-4% of the adult population [1]. Studies conducted in different populations indicate that the prevalence of the disease is 3.1-7.5% in men and 2.1-4.5% in women [2,3,4]. A total number of apneas and hypopneas per hour is named as apnea-hypopnea

index (AHI) and the number of AHI per hour of daily sleep is verified the diagnosis of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome [5]. The severity of disease according to AHI values are categorized as mild ($5 \leq \text{AHI} < 15$), moderate ($15 \leq \text{AHI} < 30$), severe ($\text{AHI} \geq 30$) OSAS [1]. Studies have demonstrated that the most privilege and effective treatment for obstructive sleep apnea syndrome is continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy [6,7,8]. Continuous positive airway pressure in the treatment of OSAS was first used by Colin Sullivan et al. in 1981 [9]. This treatment aims keeping the upper respiratory tract open during sleeping, regulating respiration and sleep quality of the person. Therefore, this device needs to be used during the sleep every night [10,11]. The effectiveness of the treatment is closely related to the duration and frequency of positive airway pressure (PAP) device used. Studies in current literature have shown that the compliance rate varies between 29-83% [12,13,14].

Along with different opinions about device compliance for

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Satisfaction Status	Point
Very Bad	1
Bad	2
Average	3
Good	4
Very Good	5

Fig.1. Satisfaction survey.

effective treatment, the overall device use rate should be > 70% and the use of device within 4 hours or longer per night is considered as "adequate compliance" [15,16]. Device compliance is not only related to patient-related factors but also about the mask and the device-related factors. Patient compliance is the essential key topic to improve the success rate of continuous positive airway pressure treatment in the patients that have obstructive sleep apnea syndrome.

In this study, we aimed to determine the factors affecting device compliance at an early stage in patients with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome who underwent auto-CPAP therapy.

Materials and methods

After local ethics committee approval (registration ID 18/06), we retrospectively evaluated the data of all obstructive sleep apnea syndrome patients that underwent auto-CPAP therapy between July 2014 and May 2017. Patients were divided into two groups according to the compliance rates, group 1 with adequate compliance and group 2 with inadequate compliance. More than 70% of device use was considered as "adequate compliance" [15,16] and assessed according to the auto-CPAP device memory card records at the end of the first month of treatment. Patient demographics, medical history, body mass index (kg/m²), pre and post-treatment Epworth sleepiness score (ESS) [18], pretreatment PSG results (according to the rules of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine) [17], posttreatment 4th week follow-up patient symptoms and patient-reported device side effects (e.g., skin irritation, device noise, and morning headache and the like), and device records (including mean and minimum-maximum device use periods) were documented and reviewed. Disease severity according to AHI was also noted as mild ($5 \leq \text{AHI} < 15$), moderate ($15 \leq \text{AHI} < 30$) and severe ($\text{AHI} \geq 30$) OSAS.

Additionally, in our clinic, we are routinely using a general satisfaction questionnaire (fig 1) to evaluate the general patient satisfaction levels related to the continuous positive airway pressure device. The results of this general satisfaction questionnaire also evaluated between groups. All included patients had used nasal masks for continuous positive airway pressure therapy. Only the patients with missing data at the posttreatment 4th-week follow-up were excluded from the study.

Statistical Analysis:

SPSS for Mac Version 20.00 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used for the statistical analysis of the data obtained at the end of the study. Continuous data were tested for normal distribution using the Kolmogorov Smirnov test. Data with a normal distribution are presented as mean and standard deviation and compared by T-test, and non-normally distributed data

are presented as median and interquartile range and compared by Mann-Whitney U test. Categorical data were presented as counts and percentages and compared by Chi-square test. P values < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 275 consecutive patients with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome who underwent auto-CPAP therapy were included in our study. Of these 275, 35 patients were excluded from the study because of missing device records. Finally, data of 240 patients were analyzed. 204 (85%) patients were male, and 36 (%15) patients were female. Mean age of the study population was 46.82 ± 13.04 and mean body mass index (BMI) was 29.58 ± 4.03 . The mean duration of device use was 26.15 ± 4.89 days, and mean duration of device use per night was 5.31 ± 1.32 hours for commencement four weeks. There were 146 cases in group 1 and 94 cases in group 2, and the compliance rate in the entire population was found to be 60.8%. There was no statistically significant difference between groups among all demographic data, including pre-treatment PSG parameters and pulmonary function tests (PFT) values (Table-1). After four weeks course of treatment, a statistically significant difference was observed between the two groups in terms of skin irritation (21.8% vs 78.8%), device noise (100% vs 0%) and morning headache (14.3% vs %85.7) complaints ($p < 0.05$ for all). All these complaints were higher in the group with low compliance.

Moreover, satisfaction, mean AHI scores, ESS scores and ESS differences were also significantly different between the two groups (Table-2). Mean duration of device use was positively correlated with device compliance and patient satisfaction. Furthermore, positive correlations were also obtained between device compliances and patient satisfaction.

Discussion

Studies about CPAP therapy in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome indicate that more effective compliance can be achieved, especially with the effective use of the device during the initial period of treatment [13,19,20]. In this study, we evaluated the factors affecting the treatment compliance in the initial four weeks of auto-CPAP treatment in 240 patients with obstructive sleep apnea syndrome. We divided the cases into two groups according to their compliance rates. While group 1 consisted of the patients who had adequate compliance, group 2 consisted of the patients who had insufficient compliances. We tried to determine the factors affecting the compliance rates among these two groups. Previous studies in English literature related to the CPAP device compliance have reported different rates ranging between 29-83% [12,13,14,21-23]. In a study conducted by Hasim B. et al., the complaints reported by the patients were found to be 80.9%. However, as a result of examination of the device records, the compliance rate was 48.9% in the same patient group [22]. Another study from the United Kingdom [24] reported that long-term compliance rate was 76%. Consistent with the previous studies we found early patient compliance 60.8% for the whole study population. Also, studies in the literature with constant pressure continuous positive airway pressure devices and variable pressure CPAP (auto-CPAP) devices have demonstrated no long-term differences in treatment efficacy and compliance [25,26,27]. The daily use time of the device in our study was 5.31 ± 1.32 hours per night. In another study conducted in our country in this regard, the average daily use was

Table 1 Comparison of the groups before Auto-CPAP therapy

		Group 1 (Sufficient Compliance) (n=146)	Group 2 (Insufficient Compliance) (n=94)	p-value
Female/Male (n)		20/126	16/78	NS
Age,years		46.27±12.66	47.68±13.64	NS
BMI,kg/m2		29.92±4.44	29.05±3.24	NS
Smoking History	Smoking,yes/no	72/74	46/48	NS
	Pack year smoking	9.47±12.26	9.53±12.45	NS
Family Features	Marital Status (Bachelor/Married)	14/88(0.16)	28/110(0.25)	NS
	Duration of Marriage, years	17.96±13.75	20.02±15.06	NS
	Number of family members at home	3.13±1.10	3.26±1.47	NS
Educational Status	Primary School	10(35.7)	18(64.3)	NS
	Secondary School	6(30)	14(70)	NS
	High School	50(52.1)	46(47.9)	NS
	University	36(37.5)	60(62.5)	NS
ESS (Before Treatment)		15.13±3.75	15.27±3.63	NS
PSG Findings	AHI	40.96±23.61	42.46±27.97	NS
	REM AHI	38.12±27.82	36.81±27.81	NS
	OSAS Severity			
	Mild OSAS	10(%62.5)	6(%37.5)	NS
	Moderate OSAS	42(%56.8)	32(%43.2)	NS
	Severe OSAS	94(%62.7)	56(%37.3)	NS
	Mean Disturbance Index	28.80±18.74	30.48±23.46	NS
PFT	FVC, % predicted	99.91±12.95	128.65±151.98	NS
	FEV1,% predicted	102.04±13.40	101.56±17.25	NS
	FEV/FVC,%	98.17±99.18	83.16±6.64	NS
The number of comorbid diseases		0.63±0.96	0.86±1.15	NS
Definition of abbreviations: BMI: Body Mass Index, ESS: Epworth Sleepiness Scale, AHI: Apnea-Hypopnea Index, REM: Rapid Eye Movement, FVC: Forced Vital Capacity, FEV1: Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 s, PSG: Polysomnography, PFT: Pulmonary Function Test				

Table 2 Comparison of the groups after Auto-CPAP therapy

		Group 1 (Sufficient Compliance) (n=146)	Group 2 (Insufficient Compliance) (n=94)	p-value
Patient with a complaint (n)		35(33.3)	70(66.7)	0.011
Complaint	Skin Irritation	10(21.2)	37(78.8)	<0.001
	Nose Drying	10 (13.8)	23(69.7)	NS
	Mask Odor	12(40)	18(60)	NS
	Device Noise	0(0)	6(100)	0.040
	Headache at morning	2(14.3)	12(85.7)	0.028
	Satisfaction Point	1	4(16.7)	20(83.3)
	2	2(11.1)	16(88.9)	<0.001
	3	54(73.1)	14(26.9)	<0.001
	4	54 (67.5)	26(32.5)	<0.001
	5	44(66.7)	22(33.3)	<0.001
AHI	Mean AHI of The Device	2.88±1.75	4.76±2.07	<0.001
	AHI Difference	37.78±23.53	38.85±29.97	NS
ESS	ESS of The 1st Month	1.53±2.71	4.12±5.09	0.001
	ESS Difference	12.60±3.92	11.14±5.31	0.016
The Mean Daily Usage Duration, min.		356.91±55.57	259.08±74.35	<0.001
Definition of abbreviations: ESS: Epworth Sleepiness Scale, AHI: Apnea-Hypopnea Index				

found to be 6.3 ± 2.3 hours [28]. In another study, it was found to be 5.3 hours [24]. In general, device compliance has a positive correlation with increasing daily device use time. There is some studies evaluating whether factors such as demographic data and educational status of patients affect treatment response. In a study conducted by Soltaninejad F, treatment compliance was found to be higher in non-smokers, well- educated and younger patients. Also, BMI > 35 was associated with increased treatment compliance [29]. They have suggested that patients with high BMI probably benefit more and ignored their complaints. In another study showing the relationship between high BMI and treatment compliance, Syed et al. could not be able to demonstrate any correlation between compliance and age, gender, and cigarette smoking [23]. Several other studies have reported that education status and demographics do not affect treatment compliance [30]. Our study was consistent with these previous studies. In our study, we found no difference between education levels, smoking, marital status, BMI and treatment compliance. Although it was not statistically significant, treatment compliance was higher in cases with high severity of the disease. In general, studies in this regard suggest that events with high AHI values are more compatible with treatment [31,32]. However, several studies have reported that disease severity is not related to compliance [23].

We found that ESS scores were high before treatment and

decreased significantly with treatment in both groups of patients. This reduction was more significant in the group with adequate treatment compliance. In a study of Hussain et al. regarding long-term compliance with continuous positive airway pressure treatment, it was found that there was a significant reduction in ESS scores with treatment and this reduction was greater in compliant patients [23]. Another study concluded that a 44% reduction in ESS scores was obtained with CPAP therapy within the first two weeks and the lowest mean ESS score was observed at six months [33].

Since there are no validated satisfaction surveys assessing device compliance, usually surveys indicating the quality of life are used for this purpose [34]. Balachandran et al. prepared a CPAP perception questionnaire for predicting patient compliance. They showed a significant correlation between questions and compliance with one-month CPAP treatment [21]. In our clinic, we are using a five-point scale (very bad, bad, average, good and very good) to evaluate the general satisfaction levels of the device. This is not an international or widely used scoring system, but according to our experience gives valuable information about patient satisfaction. All patients were assessed with this general satisfaction questionnaire. As expected, patients' satisfaction with continuous positive airway pressure devices increased with increasing treatment compliance. This condition was supported by the fact that the Apnea-Hypopnea Index and

ESS scores at 1st month were lower in the group with adequate treatment compliance. This also shows the efficacy of PAP therapy. Similar results are supported by various studies in the literature [12,28,33].

The side effects experienced by the patients are one of the foremost reasons for withdrawal of the treatment. The most significant side effects are mask related side effects and the type of mask used in conjunction with PAP therapy [35,36]. Compliance with treatment generally decreases in cases with a higher incidence of complaints, especially about the mask [6,14]. Borel et al. [36] reported that the use of nasal masks was the first type of mask to enhance treatment compliance. It has also been reported that side effects associated with the mask also affect compliance with PAP therapy and occur in approximately 30-70% of patients [14]. In our study, all patients had used a nasal mask, and so there were no differences regarding the type of mask used. However, some complaints, which we thought to be related to the general characteristics and quality of the materials, were significantly important in terms of treatment compliance. Among them, the most common complaints were skin irritation due to mask, device noise and morning headache.

Limitations

Our study has some limitations. First, it has a retrospective and single-centre design. The relatively small sample size of the current study indicates the need to validate the findings in a larger patient cohort. Despite these limitations, we believe that our results propose a need for further studies. Since the vast majority of the population was male, our findings cannot be extrapolated, female individuals.

Conclusion

As a result, we can say that patient-reported device side effects to decrease the compliance rates. On the other hand, increasing OSAS severity is positively correlated with device compliance. Another striking result of our study is that with increasing CPAP device use, which is the most effective treatment method in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome disease, the efficiency of treatment and patient satisfaction are increased significantly. These results may lead us to encourage our patients for the increasing usage of the CPAP device.

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